

On Mining Platinum and Mining Data: Is data the new Gold?

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Abstract: Data mining comes from mining, that is, the extraction of minerals from the Earth. On the occasion of the retirement of Prof. Nina Thornhill, a pioneer in the area of data mining techniques in the process industries, the authors are exploring the similarities of mining data and mining rock, are establishing the current state of mining data in minerals processing plants and summarizing lessons learnt over the years. Despite advances made, there are still opportunities for research to automate data mining in an industrial context.

Keywords: Data mining, platinum production, minerals processes, control, University of Pretoria.

1. INTRODUCTION

Professor Nina Thornhill has been at the forefront of developing methods to gain information and insight from operational data in the process industries. The techniques she has discovered over the year address problems in the processes to improve productivity.

Her research results are at the centre of hype topics such as Industrie 4.0 and Data Science. She uses statistical methods and algorithms to extract insight and knowledge from the data in order to find and diagnose faults and to understand the operation better. An overview of Prof. Thornhill work can be found on the Nordic Process Control Workshop website where she was the award recipient in 2019.

The personal connections of the authors to Prof. Thornhill originates from the fact that Margret Bauer, after completing her PhD with her moved to the University of Pretoria to conduct her postdoctoral studies with Ian Craig. Ian Craig in turn spent a sabbatical working at Imperial College London, in the electrical engineering department before dedicating much of his time to IFAC and acting as president from 2011-2014. Derik le Roux has completed and John Burchell is currently conducting his PhD with Prof. Ian Craig. All have worked on many mining problems and encountered vast amounts of data.

In recent years, data has been declared to be the new currency. This is mostly mentioned in the context of consumer data. For example, by collecting the data that consumers leave in their browsing history via cookies, Amazon generates 30% of its revenue based on recommendations compiled from this data, i.e., they generate revenue from data.

But is data really the new gold? Does this apply to the process industry? Sometimes a process historian feels more like a data dump or graveyard than a gold mine. We would like to use this opportunity to look into how valuable process

data is and can be by investigating common aspects between data mining and mining precious metals such as platinum.

In the following, we discuss what we think is currently achievable with data mining, what data is available and the lessons we learnt from looking at data. This is supplemented by analogies from other disciplines – data science is not only prominent in the process industries but in many other fields such as banking, consumer software and Internet technologies. This contribution is concluded with challenges that prevail. Prof. Thornhill's work is the beginning. There remain many unsolved problems and more work for future generations of PhD students to come.

2. DATA ANALYTICS, SCIENCE AND MINING

Data is generated in abundance in the process industries. Because storage has been very affordable for many years now, data historians retain more information for longer. There are different terminologies that have made it into the public domain and are now household expressions: data science, big data, data analytics or, if you want it all: big data analytics and science. The common idea for all of them is to exploit data to gain insight.

Data mining has been a buzzword since the 1990s when large databases became ubiquitous for businesses and operations. It is a very accurate description of the activity that is involved when looking into extracting information from large amount of data: many “stones” must be turned over until a bit of information is learned. This can only be achieved in a systematic way with appropriate tools, which is exactly what is done.

Data mining also reminds us that looking into the data is an engineering task. It requires domain knowledge – just like it requires engineering skills to mine rocks and process it to extract precious metals from rocks.

Figure 1. Mining for platinum and data mining.

3. PLATINUM MINING

Here we will briefly look into how many resources are spent on mining. Describing the mining process helps to understand how much effort goes into extraction of precious metals. South Africa has the largest reserves in the world: about 70% of all platinum is found in the region that is called the Platinum belt. But even if the ore is extracted from a very rich part, there will still only be about one to four grams of platinum in one ton of rock.

The process to extract the platinum is extremely energy and labour intensive. The rock needs to be blasted or dug out. Larger rocks are first ground to smaller rocks then and converted into slurry in the grinding and milling process where water and chemicals are added. In the flotation process, air bubbles are inserted at the bottom. The platinum attaches itself to the air bubbles and rises to the surface where it is skimmed off. And then the flotation top product is concentrated even further.

4. MINING DATA AND PLATINUM TAKES RESOURCES

Mining platinum not only takes energy, water and chemicals but also time. The time from mine to platinum is about one and a half months. In that sense, data mining is similar to mining platinum, see Figure 1. Data mining extracts a small amount of precious information from a large database. To gain insight and information from data, it is necessary to invest time and energy just like when mining platinum.

Curiously, mining platinum is an industrial production process and data is generated in large quantities. In short: We can now mine data from a mining process. At one of the largest platinum producers, Anglo Platinum, 979,000 data points are generated every second across the entire company. Considering that 28,000 tones of platinum are produced per year this means that every gram of platinum produced generates 1 million data points.

5. FAULTS ADDRESSED WITH DATA MINING

The idea of data mining in the process industries is to make sure the process operates safely and efficiently. In an ideal world, all process measurements are at their desired points and do not fluctuate. Unfortunately, this is never the case in

real life. The reason for this can be attributed to the following things that can go wrong:

- Actuators do not work linearly as expected;
- Sensors do not record the process measurements accurately but develop systemic faults such as an offset or poor analogue to digital conversion;
- Controllers can be tuned poorly and deteriorate the performance of the process;
- Sometimes the process was not designed correctly. A pipe and valve may have been designed too small which may result in saturation.
- External disturbances can affect the process such as inconsistent feed quality or temperature fluctuations caused by the weather.

A whole new complexity comes from the fact that the worst problems are the ones that travel through the process and affect a large number of process variables. Not only does the performance deteriorate even further, it will also be more difficult to find the root cause of the disturbance. Prof. Thornhill therefore dedicated a part of her research to plant-wide approaches and root cause analysis.

6. WHAT KIND OF DATA CAN BE MINED?

The data that is recorded and stored during process operations today increased exponentially over the last decades. The data also became more complex as it stems from a number of different sources. There is data from the plant historian which captures the physical quantities such as flow, temperature, pressure and level measurements. There is also the control loop data such as controller set-points and outputs.

Looking closer, the plant historian contains even more information: switching data is kept and whether the loop is in manual or in automatic. There is more: electrical data from the motors and pumps, valve positioning data, intelligent sensors, video cameras and condition monitoring systems are just some examples. Data about the health of the process control system is maintained, communication status is tracked, and information from the advanced process control system, such as the predictions, is kept.

In short, today's process industries are drowning in data.

Using the data intelligently is the difficulty. When digging into the data, process faults can be easily explained through intelligent crosschecks. For example, a disturbance affects the flotation process because the model predictive controller (MPC) in the previous processing step, the milling, was switched off. Looking at the plant historian on its own just shows that the disturbance miraculously appeared and disappeared. When combining the start/end point with the on/off information from the MPC the cause is evident. However, to combine the information requires expert knowledge.

7. LESSONS LEARNT

There are some hard lessons that every engineer venturing into the arena of data analytics need to learn to tackle problems in the process industries. Six important ones are the following:

1. Lots of data is not a cop-out for process understanding: The reason why we cannot let computer scientists alone take over the task of developing tools for data-driven process analysis is that we need to understand the underlying process at hand. Data on its own is meaningless; we need context for the data. This can be in the form of process and instrumentation diagrams (P&IDs), operator screens or process schematics. It takes both a love for process data and for process understanding to come off with useful tools that can improve the performance of an industrial process.
2. 'F' in feedback also stands for forgiving: Every process control engineer at some stage in their career needs to marvel at the simplicity and beauty of feedback control using a proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller. Feedback control can be remarkably forgiving in the sense that even a poorly tuned PID controller can produce sufficient set-point tracking results. Surely there must be a better control strategy than this simple algorithm that fits into one line of code? However, the truth is that most processes are benign. They can be described as first order time delay systems, which will – unless seriously provoked with aggressive tuning parameters – never become unstable. The performance of these control loops may not be as optimal as it could be, but it will not be worth tuning it. Focus on the important loop and those few that have the potential of becoming unstable.
3. Learn from the good operator: Just like with dentists, teachers, lawyers and – let's face it – even engineers, there are good and not so good operators. The good operator will have seen many different situations and have learned from them. The knowledge of a good operator is invaluable and should be taken into account. Unfortunately, there can be a disconnect between the corporate engineering department and the plant personnel on site. As an academic researcher you will obviously not change that relationship but it's recommended to work with partners where the relationship exists. Speak to the operator with the best performance. Just like with the dentists and lawyers, there will be noticeable differences.
4. Industrial data will never look as expected: The engineer who has never looked at data from an industrial process will likely be unfamiliar with some of the challenges encountered when preparing or interpreting industrial data. The usual tasks of outlier removal and noise filtering may be expected, but how should we treat the different modes of operation of an industrial process? Startup and shutdown modes can easily be identified in the time series, and would likely be excluded from the analysis altogether. However, there may be less familiar modes like housekeeping events, where the plant is washed with water that when returned to the process results in unmeasured disturbances. Identifying these less familiar modes will require knowledge of plant operation (point 3), while knowing how to treat them during the analysis will require process knowledge (point 1). In addition, although plants are design to operate at an optimal steady-state point, the data from plants rarely conform to "textbook" steady-state operation. Disturbances and process variations will always perturb the process and manifest as undulations in data.
5. Seeing is not necessarily believing: Although there is an abundance of data, questions should always be asked regarding the quality of the data. Measurements on process industries are generally very noisy, the abrasive nature of the environment often cause measurement devices to fail, and the varying mineralogy of the rock may require instruments to be calibrated frequently. When data from a certain period of operation is used to build models of the process, special care should be taken that the measurements are accurate and reliable.
6. Not everything can be measured: There are certain measurements which are important for process operation, but which cannot be taken. For example, the volume of balls within grinding mills has a significant impact on the breaking of ore, but there is no reliable instrumentation available to measure this variable. Similarly, air recovery for flotation cells determines the performance of the cells, but cannot yet be measured directly. A series of other sometimes difficult to achieve measurements needs to be made to estimate these variables.

8. OPEN CHALLENGES

Data science tools have been hugely successful in other fields and are also to some extent successful in the process industries. There are challenges that need to be overcome and we believe the following two are most urgent:

Lack of categories for classification and lack of evidence

A successful example of using data analytics is in banking data, where data can be used to detect fraud by examining patterns and anomalies in historical data. The difference to the process is that there are many instances of known fraud and clearly normal, non-fraudulent transactions. The case is not so easy for faults in process data. Faults develop over long periods of time during which changing conditions can change the pattern. Also, not enough data is available for verified faults. An algorithm may have picked up valve stiction as the root cause of a disturbance but unless it is confirmed by physically replacing the valve, examining it and

comparing the before and after trends, you cannot be certain that the fault actually was stiction. During the day-to-day running of a plant engineers and operators have more pressing issues than correctly classifying data. This may have to change.

Getting people to use the tools

The arguably most difficult part of data analytics is to get operators and engineers to use the tools. The reason is partly that most tools are cumbersome to access and/or have a poor human-machine interface. Another reason could be that people are overworked, have other priorities and no incentives to find faults in data using the tools. However, often it is a question of robustness. If a valve stiction detection algorithm gives a result that says '60% chance of valve stiction', the user needs guidance and more important experience to know what that means and what actions result from 60% stiction. Is this a strong enough indication to change the valve at the next shut-down? Is it necessary to generate more tests?

Tools have to be robust

Getting people to use the tools is closely related to the reliability or robustness of the results. If the results are robust, that is, they are consistently give the correct results with no false negatives and positives, the method can be automated completely. If the tools are 90% robust then the human certainly needs to be in the loop. Figure 2 shows the relationship between robustness and user involvement. What often happens is that the robustness is over-estimated. As a result, tools that require an expert are used by non-expert people or are automated, don't work and are then switched off.

platinum in it. To extract the valuable data, the insight, we need clever and useful data mining tools, such as developed by Prof. Thornhill over her the course of her career. And these tools, which have to be in appropriate hands.

We wish Prof. Thornhill all the best for her retirement and would like to thank her for her contributions to the research community.

Figure 2. Robustness versus user involvement: Less robust methods require more user involvement and everything above a certain threshold will result in a clash of expectations and in underusing of tools.

9. CONCLUSIONS

So is data the new gold? We think that the answer is a conditional, cautious yes: data does contains gold. The entire database on its own is only a ton of rock with four grams of